

ANALYSIS OF ORAL HEALTH STATUS IN EGYPTIAN PATIENTS COMPARED TO OTHER AFRICAN COUNTRIES

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Abstract. The problem of poor oral health has been relevant for many decades. It is especially acute among those segments of the population that have a low level of education and income. Harmful habits, such as smoking, exacerbate the problem. The study showed that the state of the oral cavity in rural Egyptians is low and tends to increase.

Keywords: oral health, rural Egyptian population, smoking, life factors

Introduction. The article presents data on the main diseases of the oral cavity of the rural inhabitants of Egypt. Their main manifestations and causes are shown. The data are compared with those of residents of other countries of the African continent.

Aim of investigation. The purpose of this study was to study the manifestations of the main pathological processes of the oral cavity among the rural population of Egypt and compare them with the same indicators of the inhabitants of other African countries according to literature data.

Materials and methods. 530 patients aged 20 to 70 years were examined. The patients were divided on 113 male patients and 417 female patients. The number of carious teeth, periodontal disease and the presence of oral cancer were determined. Additionally, a WHO questionnaire was used, which contained

questions about life factors, such as age, sex, educational levels, income, smoking and oral hygiene measures [1].

Results: Among the examined patients of the rural population of Egypt, men made up 21%, women 79%. The results of using the WHO questionnaire showed that the number of people with higher education was 4.7%, 50% had secondary education and 35.5% were illiterate. At the same time, 27.5% of rural residents were well-off, had an income, and 72.5% were without income. As for socio-economic aspects, including behavioral risk factors (oral hygiene procedures and smoking), only 34.3% of patients brush their teeth, 13.8% were male smokers. Among male patients, about 80% had an unsatisfactory oral condition, and only 20% had a good oral condition. 73.61% of women with poor oral hygiene turned out to be, and 25.89% of them had a satisfactory state of oral health. The % of Egyptian patients with periodontal pockets is 56% which is very high in contrast with other African countries which have lower percentages (Zimbabwe 23%, Tanzania 10%, Ghana 37%, Burkina Faso 46%). The % of Egyptian men smokers is 34% and women is 0,2 %. The Death rate from Oral Cancer Deaths in Egypt is 1.16 from 100.000 people in contrast with other African countries which have higher death rates (Nigeria (2.44), Ethiopia (2.58), DR Congo (2.21), Tanzania (6.73), South Africa (3.18)) [2, 3,4].

Conclusions. The results of research have shown that there is a direct relationship between smoking and oral diseases. Female Egyptian patients have lower dental problems than men. Cigarettes, smokeless tobacco, and other forms of tobacco cause oral cancer, gum disease, and other oral health problems. In Egypt, the number of adult cigarette smokers is increasing annually at a rate of 4-5%. At the same time, in many other countries, adult tobacco consumption is declining or remains at the same level. Thus, it can be concluded that the main factors of the occurrence of a low level of oral health among the rural population of Egypt are the lack of measures for oral hygiene, low level of education or lack of education, low income and low awareness of the population about

measures to prevent dental diseases. In general, indicators of Egyptians are lower than that of other African countries.

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